

ANALYSIS OF CHILD MARRIAGE FACTORS ON THE INCIDENCE OF CHRONIC ENERGY DEFICIENCY (CED) IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Abstract

In the 21st century, the phenomenon of underage marriage of young girls still occurs in developing countries. The factor of early marriage is the main focus in preventing maternal and neonatal emergencies. One of the factors of early pregnancy is adolescence and family income which are considered to be factors that can increase the potential for CED in mothers during pregnancy. The purpose of this study was to analyze the factors of child marriage on the incidence of Chronic Energy Deficiency (CED) in women of childbearing age in the working area of the Biji Nangka Health Center, Sinjai Regency in 2024. Quantitative method with a cross-sectional study approach variable Knowledge, Attitude and Incidence of CED. The population in this study were all Reproductive-Age Woman (RAW) 20 years in the working area of the Samaenre Health Center, totaling 30 people, Total Sampling technique. The results of the study used the test Chi-Square shows that there is a relationship between RAW knowledge about CED (p -value = 0.000) and RAW attitude about CED (p -value = 0.002) with the incidence of CED at Health Center, so it is recommended that the Health Office needs to make health promotion efforts about the importance of pregnancy at a healthy reproductive age and the importance of knowledge about factors related to CED.

Keywords: RAW, Knowledge, Attitude and Incidence of CED

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the phenomenon of marrying young underage girls still occurs in many developing countries. According to United Nations (UN) data, 1 in 9 girls in developing countries will marry at the relatively young age of 15 years. If this tradition does not change, it is estimated that by 2020, every year, 14.2 million girls will get married (Prihartini & Rosidah, 2022). According to data from the Indonesian Ministry of Health, the maternal mortality rate in 2020 was around 189 per 100 thousand births (BPS, 2023). Data obtained from the profile of the South Sulawesi Provincial Health Service in 2020, the highest Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) was in Makassar City (27,191 cases), the lowest in Selayar Regency (2,159 cases), while in Kab. Sinjai (6,770) (Sul-Sel, 2021). The increase in early marriage could be a demographic problem. It is true, early marriage has many negative impacts on various aspects of life. In terms of education, children who marry early often stop continuing their education. Early marriage often creates a new cycle of poverty. UNICEF's Global Database (2020) even notes that child marriage costs at least 1.7% of a country's national income. Apart from that, early marriage easily leads to domestic violence, adultery and divorce because children are not yet mentally mature. On the other hand, early marriage will endanger the health of the expectant mother, because the child's anatomy is not yet ready for fertilization and birth, and pregnancy can cause complications for the pregnant mother. Children born from early marriage are 1.5 times more likely to die in the first 28 days (Hermambang, A., C., & Sanusi, 2021). The high maternal mortality rate (MMR) is caused by bleeding, hypertension, infection, prolonged labor and abortion. Bleeding during childbirth is the highest cause of maternal death (28%). Anemia and chronic energy deficiency (CED) in pregnant women are the main causes of bleeding (Aprilia, 2020). Chronic energy deficiency (CED) is a

condition where pregnant women experience malnutrition for a long period of time (chronic or chronic) resulting in health problems, inability to meet the increased nutritional needs during pregnancy (Rafiani, Qariati, & Anggraini, 2020). There were 167 marriage registrations at the Sinjai Borong District Religious Affairs Office in 2021 and 28 people registered child marriages (16.8%), in 2022 there were 120 people and 17 child marriages were recorded (14.2%), in 2023 as many as 149 and 33 people (22.1%) registered child marriages and by August 2024 there were 120 people recorded with 30 child marriages (25%). Factors that are considered to be related to the incidence of CED in WUS include economic status, socio-economic conditions which cause low education, birth spacing that is too close which causes poor nutritional status in pregnant women, gender inequality, mothers who are too young or teenagers, and employment. that they usually have. nutritional importance. lower if not balanced with proper nutrition (Rosita & Rusmimpong, 2022). The impact of chronic energy deficiency (CED) on the fetus includes the risk of stunted fetal growth, miscarriage or abortion, stillbirth, neonatal death, birth defects, blood in newborns, birth asphyxia (death in the womb), and Low Birth Weight (LBW) (Rafiani, Qariati, & Anggraini, 2020).

2. METHODOLOGY

The method that will be used in this research is a quantitative method with a cross sectional study approach to analyze the factors of child marriage and the incidence of Chronic Energy Deficiency (CED) in women of childbearing age at the Biji Nangka Community Health Center, Sinjai Regency in 2024. This research was conducted at the Biji Nangka Community Health Center, Sinjai Regency. The population in this study were all RAW mothers aged < 20 years in the working area of the Biji Nangka Health Center, Sinjai Regency in 2024, totaling 30 people. The sampling technique used was total sampling, where the entire population was sampled in this research. The research instrument consists of an observation sheet and a questionnaire, The results of the study used the test Chi-Square.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Univariate Analysis

a. Distribution of RAW Knowledge about CED

The research results show that of the 30 WUS involved in This research is based on the level of knowledge about CED of the majority of RAW with sufficient knowledge in the category of 14 respondents (46.7%), good for 9 respondents (30%) and less for 7.

b. Distribution of RAW Attitudes regarding CED

The research results showed that of the 30 RAW based on attitude each positive attitude 15 respondents (50%) and negative 15 respondents (50%).

c. Distribution of CED occurrences in RAW regarding CED

The research results show that out of 30 based on incidents The majority of CED did not experience CED as many as 19 respondents (63.3%) and 11 respondents (36.7%) experienced CED.

3.2 Bivariate Analysis

a. The relationship between knowledge and the incidence of CED in RAW

Knowledge	Chronic Energy Deficiency (CED)						p-value
	CED		Non CED		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Baik	2	22.2	7	77.8	9	100	0.000
Cukup	2	14.3	12	85.7	14	100	
Kurang	7	1.00	0	0	7	100	
Total	11	36.7	19	63.3	30	100	

The research results showed that of the 30 respondents based on the level of knowledge in the sufficient category, 14 respondents did not experience CED, 12 respondents (85.7%), and 2 respondents (14.3%) experienced CED. The majority of 9 respondents had good knowledge and did not experience CED, 7 respondents (77.8%) and 2 respondents (22.2%) experienced CED. There were 7 respondents in the poor category of knowledge, where all respondents experienced CED (100%). The results of the Chi-Square statistical test obtained a p-value = 0.000 which is smaller than the value $\alpha=0.05$, which means "Ha" is accepted and "H0" is rejected so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between RAW knowledge about CED and the incidence of CED at the Biji Nangka Health Center District Sinjai in 2024. From the results of this research, it can be assumed that RAW ignorance about CED is influenced by their too young age and low level of education so that not having experience about CED is the cause of RAW low knowledge about CED. In this study, the majority of RAW had poor knowledge, but there were several RAW with good and sufficient levels of knowledge. Variations in the level of knowledge of RAW are influenced by several factors ranging from educational level, age, experience and sources of information where they can access information about CED. This is in accordance with the theory put forward by Mubarak (2011) in (Purba, Sinaga, Ardiansyah, & Sihura, 2021) stating that there are 7 factors that influence a person's knowledge: education level, age occupation, interests, experience, environment, and information. Knowledge or cognitive domain is a very important domain in shaping a person's actions (Retni & Puluhalawa, 2021). A study found that 53 Knowledge-based behavior lasts longer than behavior without a knowledge base (Utami, Yusuf, & Nurjannah, 2022). People who lack nutritional knowledge will behave in choosing foods that appeal to the five senses and will not make choices based on the nutritional value of the food. On the other hand, those who have good knowledge tend to use more rational considerations and knowledge about the nutritional value of food so that they will not experience chronic energy deficiency (Aida, Asrinawaty, & Enadi, 2022)

b. The relationship between RAW attitudes about CED and the occurrence of CED

Attitudes	Chronic Energy Deficiency (CED)						p-value
	CED		Non CED		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Positif	1	6.7	14	93.3	15	100	0.002
Negative	10	66.7	5	33.3	15	100	
Total	11	36.7	19	63.3	30	100	

The research results showed that of the 30 respondents based on the positive attitude category, the majority did not experience CED, 14 respondents (93.3%) and 1 respondent experienced CED (6.7%). In RAW with a negative attitude category, the majority experienced CED, 10 respondents (66.7%) and those who did not experience CED, 5 respondents (33.3%). The results of the Chi-Square statistical test obtained a p-value = 0.002, which is smaller than the value $\alpha=0.05$, which means "Ha" is accepted and "H0" is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between RAW attitudes regarding CED and the incidence of CED at the Biji Nangka Community Health Center District Sinjai in 2024. From the results of this research it can be assumed that the majority of respondents have positive attitudes about chronic energy deficiency where the respondent's attitude is influenced by several factors, including the influence of people closest to them who provide information related to CED. This research is in line with research conducted by (Arista, Widajanti, & Aruben, 2017) that more than half of young women have a positive attitude about nutrition (63.0%) with a mean score of 58.50%. Research by (Aprilianti & Purna, 2018) showed that the majority of RAW had poor knowledge, 39 respondents (55.7%) and 31 respondents (44.3%) had good knowledge. This research contradicts research conducted by (Arista, Widajanti, & Aruben, 2017) showing that of 46 young women there were 21 people (45.70%) who had CED with a median LILA size of 23.55 cm. Research by (Aprilianti & Purna, 2018) shows that the majority of respondents have attitudes in the unfavorable category, 36 respondents (51.4%) and 34 respondents (48.6%) as good. Attitude is also said to be the way you behave 55 towards someone or something that shows how you think and feel (Swarjana & SKM, 2022). Good nutritional status refers to the use of healthy foods consumed by the body.

During pregnancy, pregnant women should supplement their diet to avoid chronic energy deficiency (CED) (Faozi, 2022).

4. CONCLUSIONS

- a. Based on the level of knowledge about CED, the majority of RAW with sufficient knowledge were 14 respondents (46.7%), either 9 respondents (30%) or less, 7 respondents (23.3%).
- b. Of the 30 RAW based on their respective attitudes, 15 respondents (50%) had positive attitudes and 15 respondents (50%) had negative attitudes.
- c. Of the 30 based on the incidence of CED, the majority did not experience KEK as many as 19 respondents (63.3%) and experienced CED as many as 11 respondents (36.7%)
- d. There is a relationship between RAW knowledge about CED and the incidence of CED at the Biji Nangka District Health Center. Sinjai in 2024 (p-value=0.000).
- e. There is a relationship between the RAW attitude regarding CED and the CED incident at the Biji Nangka District Health Center. Sinjai in 2024 (p-value=0.002)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the writing team, ITKES Muhammadiyah Sidrap, and the International Conference publisher for facilitating our article.

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